

A COSSERAT CONTINUUM MODEL FOR UNCURED COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH APPLICATIONS TO PLY WRINKLE FORMATION

Timothy J. Dodwell¹, Samuel Erland and Richard Butler

Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Bath
Claverton Down, Bath, BA2 7AY, UK

¹Email: t.j.dodwell@bath.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.bath.ac.uk>

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ABSTRACT

A Cosserat continuum for uncured composite laminates is presented, and demonstrates the capability of capturing layer-wise mechanics on the macroscale without explicitly modelling individual layers. The model offers a robust approach at a fraction of the computational cost when compared to classical finite element modelling techniques. A general formulation for a 2D periodic orthotropic laminate is given, whereby essential input parameters for inter-ply shear, intra-ply shear and bending stiffnesses are determined from bespoke small-scale experiments. The Cosserat continuum model is then benchmarked against experimental measurements of a multi-layered cantilever. The paper then extends the initial small rotation formulation to account for the weakly nonlinear, geometric stress stiffening effects arising from finite Cosserat rotations. The extension demonstrates the capability of the Cosserat continuum model to predict out-of-plane ply wrinkling defects during the consolidation of a laminate over an external radius. A comparison of wrinkle profiles between those observed in a spar demonstrator and the model show good agreement.

1 INTRODUCTION

Whilst the basic advantages of composite materials are well proven, they are often compromised by high costs, long development time, and poor quality due to manufacturing defects. This is particularly the case for the complex structures found in aerospace applications. Modelling, simulation and optimisation have widespread applications to the industry, with the twin objectives of improving product quality and decreasing production time.

Fig. 1. The range of scales introduces significant complexity in the analysis of aerospace composites. From Left to Right: fibre/resin scale (5 μ m), ply scale (0.25mm), laminate scale (5-30mm) to the large-scale composite structure (> 1m).

Analysis of aerospace composites is difficult due to the complex interactions between multiple scales within the structural hierarchy: from the material scale (Fig. 1 left) up to the component (Fig. 1 right). There is a real industry need for the development of efficient models, which can predict part quality and performance, to avoid the expensive iterative ‘trial and improvement’ cycle currently employed. Robust mathematical and numerical methods are required to obtain computationally tractable solutions to such challenging problems.

1.1 Out-of-plane wrinkling defects in aerospace composites

Typically, carbon fibre composite parts are made by layering a series of thin carbon fibre layers, pre-impregnated with resin, onto a tool surface. During this lay-up process the stack of plies is consolidated at moderate temperatures and pressures to remove air trapped between layers. However, as a laminate consolidates over even a simple geometry the plies are forced to accommodate the imposed geometry of the tool surface. If the resistance to shear is too high, layers may form wrinkles. Figure 2 shows small amplitude wrinkles or folds, which have developed in the corner radius of a large-scale component. Understanding how wrinkles form during these manufacturing processes is important because, depending on their severity, they may compromise the structural integrity of the final part [1], leading in some cases to expensive wholesale rejection.

Fig. 2. (left) CT image of a typical wrinkle defect in a corner, arising due to the inability of layers to slip over one another during consolidation. (Right) Conventional macroscale stresses and moment / coupled stresses acting on a Cosserat element.

1.2 Cosserat continuum models for layered materials

The deformation or behaviour of uncured composite laminates is complex. It depends on the individual constitutive behaviour of the plies and interface, as well as the geometric constraints that arise from the layers fitting and moving together [2,3,4]. Theoretically, uncured composites can be modelled using detailed finite element calculations in which each layer and interface is defined explicitly [5]. However, such models are naturally restricted since the mesh size must be sufficiently small compared to the layer thickness. In composite applications for which the layer thickness is much smaller than the size of the macroscale structure, such models quickly become computationally unfeasible. It is therefore essential to develop continuum descriptions of uncured composite materials, which captures the average behaviour response on a scale greater than the layers, without losing the interlayer mechanics [6].

Consider a layered material made up of stiff layers separated by weak interfaces. The important observation to understand during the deformation of such a material, is to note that in general the shear stresses are non-symmetric. To see this, first consider the shear behaviour parallel to the layers. In this case the layers act like a set of shear springs in series, whereby the overall stiffness is dominated by the weak interfaces. However if a layered material is sheared perpendicular to the layering, the layers act like shear springs in parallel, and the stiff layers dominate the macro-scale behaviour. Consequently, in a general loading scenario the shear stresses are not equal, resulting in internal moments that must be equilibrated.

Here a Cosserat continuum model [7] is introduced, to describe the macroscale behaviour of uncured composite material. Cosserat continuum models introduce independent rotational degrees of freedom at each material points. Spatial gradients of these rotations measure the internal bending of the layers, modes of deformation that arise due to internal bending moments resulting from lack of symmetry in the macro-scale shear stresses. Cosserat continuum models have successfully described the macro-scale deformation of heterogeneous materials, for example granular media [8], masonry structures [9] and layered materials [10]; and recently extended to an elasto-plastic model for wrinkling in uncured

composites laminates [6]. The application of Cosserat continuum model to modelling of uncured prepreg laminates is particularly successful since composite layers are thin and separated by weak interfaces. As a result the modes of deformation introduced by the inclusion of the Cosserat rotational degree of freedom, in particular inter-layer slip and individual ply bending, are particularly relevant. The inclusion of additional modes of deformation is not required.

In section 2 a two dimensional Cosserat continuum model is introduced, which derives a homogenised macroscale Cosserat tensor of periodic orthotropic laminates. Modelling parameters for inter-ply shear, intra-ply shear and bending stiffnesses are found using bespoke experimental setups (Sec. 3). In section 4 briefly outlines how the equilibrium equations can be solved using the finite element method, and the formulation and implementation are verified against a simple set of a multi-layered cantilever experiments. Finally this paper then extends the initial small rotation formulation to account for the weakly nonlinear effects of geometric stress stiffening, which naturally arise from the inclusion of finite Cosserat rotations (Sec. 5). The extension demonstrates how the Cosserat continuum model can predict the formation of out-of-plane ply wrinkling defects during the consolidation of a laminate over an external radius as shown in Fig. 2. A comparison of wrinkle profiles between those observed in a spar demonstrator and the model is then made. The paper concludes with a brief discussion of future extensions of this work to a general 3D formulation, and implementation of more complex non-linear continuum models which include plasticity [6] and rate dependence [12].

2 COSSERAT MODEL FOR UNCURED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

Consider a layered material in the $(x_1, x_3)^T$ plane. Equilibrium (Fig. 2 (right)) of macro-scale stresses (Σ_{ij}) in the absence of body forces, gives the standard equations

$$\Sigma_{ij,j} = 0 \quad (1)$$

but also since in general the macro-scale shear stresses are not equal ($\Sigma_{13} \neq \Sigma_{31}$) moment equilibrium must also be satisfied,

$$\Sigma_{13} - \Sigma_{31} + M_{21,1} + M_{23,3} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Here M_{ij} denotes couples stresses, or moments per unit area.

Standard continuum descriptions assume kinematics (degrees of freedom) that impose symmetry of shear stresses within a continuum element. To obtain formulations capable of capturing the behaviour of a layered material on the macro-scale (i.e. greater than the layers themselves) continuum descriptions must be enriched with additional, higher-order, degrees of freedom associated with the internal bending. Here a two-dimensional, plane strain, Cosserat continuum model is introduced, in which in addition to classical translatory degrees of freedom ($\underline{u} = (u_1, u_3)^T$), a single independent macro-scale rotation (θ_2) is added at each material point. This extra degree of freedom allows macroscale kinematics capable of non-symmetric shear deformation. Consequently, Cosserat strain measures are introduced which are work conjugates to macroscale stresses Σ_{ij}

$$\gamma_{11} = u_{1,1}, \quad \gamma_{33} = u_{3,3}, \quad \gamma_{13} = u_{1,3} + \theta_2, \quad \gamma_{31} = u_{3,1} - \theta_2 \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, Cosserat curvatures, $\kappa_{2,1} = \theta_{2,1}$ and $\kappa_{2,3} = \theta_{2,3}$ are introduced. These are measures of layer-scale bending, and are work conjugates with coupled-stresses (moments per unit area) M_{ij} .

The physical significance of the Cosserat rotation and its gradients can be understood when comparing the bending of an isotropic and a layered material, Fig. 3. An additional parameter is introduced, the relative rotation between the independent Cosserat rotation and the material rotation

$$\vartheta = \frac{1}{2}(u_{1,3} - u_{3,1}) - \theta_2 \quad (4)$$

When bending an isotropic material there is no Cosserat rotation ($\theta_2 = 0$), the global rotation of the material is equal to the material rotation (i.e. $\vartheta = \frac{1}{2}(u_{1,3} - u_{3,1})$), Fig. 3 (left). For a layered material with weak interfaces (e.g. a pack of cards), the stiff layers shear relative to one another so that the Cosserat rotation and material rotation are equal, Fig. 3 (right). In this case, there is no relative macro rotation ($\vartheta = 0$), the layers all bend independently and the Cosserat curvature over a finite size element (dX) is $\kappa_{21} = 2\theta_2/dX$.

Fig. 3. A comparison of the micro-scale stress σ_{ij} distribution and Cosserat deformations measures when bending an isotropic (left) and a layered material (right).

The dual quantities are connected through the symmetric macroscale Cosserat tensors \mathbf{C}_{ijkl} and \mathbf{D}_{ijkl} of the following form (Dodwell 2015),

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{11} \\ \Sigma_{33} \\ \Sigma_{13} \\ \Sigma_{31} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{1111} & C_{1133} & & 0 \\ C_{3311} & C_{3333} & & \\ & 0 & C_{1313} & C_{1331} \\ C_{3113} & C_{3131} & & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{11} \\ \gamma_{33} \\ \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{31} \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{bmatrix} M_{21} \\ M_{23} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{2121} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \kappa_{21} \\ \kappa_{23} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

The individual terms C_{ijkl} and D_{ijkl} can be derived analytically via homogenisation of ply scale properties for periodic arrangements of orthotropic layers. Assuming the laminate is made up of periodic packages (or Representative Volume Elements - RVEs) of $K/2$ orthotropic layers ($i = 1, 3, \dots, K-1$), separated by $K/2$ orthotropic layers interfaces ($i = 2, 4, \dots, K$). The thickness of each layer is denoted h_i so that the total thickness of the periodic package $h = \sum_{i=1}^K h_i$; and $\alpha_i = h_i/h$. The elastic properties of the i^{th} layer are defined by the orthotropic matrices

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11}^{(i)} \\ \sigma_{33}^{(i)} \\ \sigma_{13}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{1111}^{(i)} & Q_{1133}^{(i)} & 0 \\ Q_{3311}^{(i)} & Q_{3333}^{(i)} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{1313}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{11}^{(i)} \\ \epsilon_{33}^{(i)} \\ \epsilon_{13}^{(i)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where $\sigma_{ij}^{(i)}$ and $\epsilon_{ij}^{(i)}$ defines the micro-scale symmetric stress and strain tensor within the i^{th} layer. Each of the values are derived by imposing a macroscale deformation isolating each of the macro-scales modes of deformation, whilst imposing equilibrium at the layer/ply scale. Here the homogenisation procedure is done for the important Cosserat terms, i.e. the shear stiffnesses and the Cosserat bending stiffness. The aim here is to highlight the physical significance of the expressions derived, and the fundamental difference between deformation of layered material with weak interfaces and isotropic material.

Firstly, the shear stiffness of the laminate parallel to the layers is derived. On the macroscale, the RVE is subject to simple shear parallel to the layering such that $\gamma_{13} \neq 0$ and $\theta_2 = \gamma_{31} = 0$. On the macroscale $\Sigma_{13} = C_{1313}\gamma_{13}$ whereas on each layer $\sigma_{13}^{(i)} = Q_{1313}^{(i)}\varepsilon_{13}^{(i)}$. Since

$$Q_{1313}^{(1)}\varepsilon_{13}^{(1)} = \Sigma_{13} = C_{1313}\gamma_{13} = C_{1313} \sum_{i=1}^K \alpha_i \varepsilon_{13}^{(i)} = C_{1313} \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{\alpha_i Q_{1313}^{(i)} \varepsilon_{13}^{(i)}}{Q_{1313}^{(i)}} \quad (7)$$

by equating the first and last expressions, and rearranging for C_{1313} it follows

$$C_{1313} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^K \frac{\alpha_i}{Q_{1313}^{(i)}} \right)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

This expression represents the weighted geometric average of shear stiffness over all layers, giving an expression similar to the overall stiffness of a set of shear springs in series. In this case the weakest layers dominate the macro-scale shear behaviour, which in this case will be the interfaces. It is noted that since the shear stresses are symmetric within each layer ($\sigma_{13}^{(i)} = \sigma_{31}^{(i)}$), then

$$C_{3113}\gamma_{13} = \Sigma_{31} = \sum_{i=1}^K \alpha_i \sigma_{31}^{(i)} = \sum_{i=1}^K \alpha_i \sigma_{13}^{(i)} = \Sigma_{13} = C_{1313}\gamma_{13} \quad (9)$$

so that the equating the first and last expression it follows that $C_{3113} = C_{1331} = C_{1313}$.

A similar process is carried out to determine the shear stiffness orthogonal to the layers, C_{3131} , so that on the macroscale, the RVE is subject to $\gamma_{31} \neq 0$ and $\theta_2 = \gamma_{13} = 0$ and $\Sigma_{31} = C_{3131}\gamma_{31}$. Equating the sum of shear forces of each layer at the left and right hand sides, with the total shear force acting on the RVE's boundaries, it follows that $\Sigma_{21} = \sum_{i=1}^K \alpha_i \sigma_{12}^{(i)}$ whereas $\varepsilon_{31}^{(i)} = \gamma_{31}$ and $Q_{1313}^{(i)} = Q_{3131}^{(i)}$, hence

$$C_{3131}\gamma_{31} = \Sigma_{31} = \sum_{i=1}^K \alpha_i Q_{1313}^{(i)} \varepsilon_{31}^{(i)} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^K \alpha_i Q_{1313}^{(i)} \right) \gamma_{31} \quad (10)$$

So therefore

$$C_{3131} = \sum_{i=1}^K \alpha_i Q_{1313}^{(i)} \quad (11)$$

This expression gives the weighted arithmetic average of the laminate shear stiffness, giving an expression similar to the overall stiffness of a set of shear springs in parallel. In this case the macroscale shear stiffness is dominated by the strongest layers. The only case in which the two shear stiffnesses C_{1313} and C_{3131} are equal is when all layers have the same shear stiffness. When this is not the case, the general deformations have non-symmetric shear stresses, generating internal moments, which the Cosserat coupled stresses equilibrate.

The internal moments cause internal (Cosserat) bending of the layers, the next step is to derive a bending stiffness (per unit area) for these internal curvatures, the Cosserat bending stiffness D_{2121} . To derive this term a deformation is imposed on the RVE such that $u_{1,3} = 0$ and $u_{3,1} = \theta_2$. Therefore on the macroscale $\Sigma_{13} = C_{1313}\theta_2 = C_{1313}u_{3,1}$, whereas for the i^{th} layer $\Sigma_{13} = \sigma_{13}^{(i)} = Q_{1313}^{(i)} \left(u_{3,1}^{(i)} + u_{1,3}^{(i)} \right)$, so that

$$u_{1,13}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{Q_{1313}^{(i)}} \Sigma_{13,1} - u_{3,11}^{(i)} = \left(\frac{C_{1313}}{Q_{1313}^{(i)}} - 1 \right) u_{3,11}^{(i)} \quad (12)$$

Noting that $\varepsilon_{11}^{(i)} = u_{1,1}^{(i)}$ is linear in x_3 , therefore integrating (12) in x_3 and substituting $u_{3,11}^{(i)} = \theta_{2,1}$ it follows that

$$\varepsilon_{11}^{(i)} = \left(\frac{C_{1313}}{Q_{1313}^{(i)}} - 1 \right) \theta_{2,1} x_3. \quad (13)$$

The moment in the i^{th} layer is $M_{21}^{(i)} = - \int_{-t_i/2}^{t_i/2} \sigma_{11}^{(i)} x_3 dx_3 = - \int_{-t_i/2}^{t_i/2} \left(Q_{1111}^{(i)} \varepsilon_{11}^{(i)} + Q_{1133}^{(i)} \varepsilon_{33}^{(i)} \right) x_3 dx_3$, assuming that $\varepsilon_{33}^{(i)} = 0$ in each layer, it follows that

$$M_{21}^{(i)} = - \int_{-t_i/2}^{t_i/2} Q_{1111}^{(i)} \varepsilon_{11}^{(i)} x_3 dx_3 = B_i \frac{Q_{1313}^{(i)} - C_{1313}}{Q_{1313}^{(i)}} \theta_{2,1} \quad (14)$$

where $B_i = \frac{1}{12} Q_{1111}^{(i)} t_i^3$ is the bending stiffness of the i^{th} layer. Therefore since the moment per unit thickness is given by $M_{21} = \frac{1}{t} \sum_{i=1}^K M_{21}^{(i)} = D_{1212} \theta_{2,1}$, it therefore follows that

$$D_{1212} = \sum_{i=1}^K \alpha_i B_i \left(\frac{Q_{1313}^{(i)} - C_{1313}}{Q_{1313}^{(i)}} \right). \quad (15)$$

To interpret D_{1212} physically, consider the two extreme cases. Firstly, if the material is isotropic such that each layer and interface is identical, the material exhibits no Cosserat effects ($D_{1212} = 0$) since the shear stiffness parallel to layers $Q_{1313}^{(i)}$ is equal to the laminate shear stiffness C_{1313} , and for this case C_{ijkl} reduces to the ply stiffness matrix Q_{ijkl} . At the other extreme when the interfaces shear stiffness is very small $Q_{1313}^{(i)} \approx 0$, yet the shear stiffness within each layer is still large $Q_{1313}^{(i)} \gg 0$. For this case, $D_{2121} \neq 0$, and all layers bend independently, where the Cosserat bending stiffness is the weighted arithmetic average the bending stiffness of each layer per unit thickness.

By applying similar deformations to the RVE (for example $\gamma_{11} \neq 0$ and $\gamma_{ij} = 0$ for all other values) and calculating equilibrium on all layers, each of the other macro scale Cosserat stiffness terms can be derived such that

$$C_{3333} = \left(\sum_{i=0}^K \frac{\alpha_i}{Q_{3333}^{(i)}} \right)^{-1} \quad \text{and} \quad C_{1133} = C_{3311} = C_{3333} \left(\sum_{i=0}^K \frac{\alpha_i Q_{1133}^{(i)}}{Q_{3333}^{(i)}} \right), \quad (16)$$

and

$$C_{1111} = \sum_{i=1}^K \left[\alpha_i Q_{1111}^{(i)} + \alpha_i Q_{1133}^{(i)} \left(\frac{C_{1133} - Q_{1133}^{(i)}}{Q_{3333}^{(i)}} \right) \right], \quad (17)$$

For specific details of the derivation of these final three terms see [6].

3 EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR DETERMINING MODELLING PARAMETERS

The Cosserat model presented requires a number of material parameters to be parameterised over a range of processing temperatures ($T = 40^{\circ}$ - 100°). This section describes the experimental procedures used to determine these modelling parameters for inter-ply shear, intra-ply shear, ply bending and consolidation behavior of AS4-8552.

Modelling parameters for inter-ply shear are calculated from experimental data collected using a custom built rig, mounted in an environmental chamber as shown in Fig. 4 (left). The rig uses a pneumatic cylinder (ii) to clamp two plates wrapped in carbon fibre pre-preg to a central plate also wrapped in pre-preg (iii). The plates are then sheared over one another using an Instron testing machine (i) at a set rate of deformation. Further details of the experimental procedure and extended tests results, which include studies of rate dependency, friction and ply angle [11,12,13]. For this contribution the gradient of the initial stress strain curves are sufficient to provide an approximation for the temperature dependent shear stiffness of the weak resin layer/interface Q_{1313}^{INT} , for which the following temperature dependent model is fitted

$$Q_{1313}^{INT} = Q_{\infty}^{INT} \exp\left(\frac{E_{INT}}{RT}\right). \quad (18)$$

Here R is the universal gas constant (8.31 J/mol K), and Q_{INT}^{∞} and E_{INT} are material parameters to be fitted to the experimental data. Figure 4 (right) shows a plot of Q_{1313}^{INT} against temperature, with a line of best fit to Eqn. (18).

Fig 4. (Left) Schematic of Inter-ply shear test rig. (Right) Plot of $\ln Q_{1313}$ against $1/T$, with a line of best fit.

Dynamical Mechanical Thermo Analysis (DMTA) is used to determine both intra-ply shear and bending stiffness of an individual ply. A sinusoidal displacement $w = w_{max} \sin(\omega t)$ is imposed on the ply at $x = \ell$, whilst both ends are clamped. To ensure representative clamped boundary conditions (with no through thickness shear or compaction) each end is set in a tab of quick dry resin with pumice additive. The vertical force f is recorded, using a 10N load cell. Due to viscous effects, the force lags behind the displacement

$$f = f_{max} \sin(\omega t + \delta) = f_{max} \cos \delta \sin \omega t + f_{max} \sin \delta \cos \omega t \quad (19)$$

where δ is the phase lag. The elastic (or rate independent) contribution is the in-phase contribution to the total force $f_e = f_{max} \cos \delta \sin(\omega t)$, assuming Timoshenko beam theory (with a shear correction factor of 6/5) it follows that

$$w_{max} = f_{max} \cos \delta \left[\frac{\ell^3}{3B} + \frac{6\ell}{5bhQ_{1313}^{PLY}} \right]. \quad (20)$$

The experiment is carried out for two different length samples ($\ell = 7.0$ mm, $\ell = 9.0$ mm) over a range of temperatures ($T = 293$ - 373 K) for a ply of thickness $h = 0.2$ mm. It is assumed that the bending stiffness of a ply and the intra-ply shear stiffness is dependent on temperature so that

$$B = B_{\infty} \exp\left(\frac{E_B}{RT}\right) \quad \text{and} \quad Q_{1313}^{PLY} = Q_{PLY}^{\infty} \exp\left(\frac{E_{PLY}}{RT}\right). \quad (21)$$

Figure 5 shows plots of experimental data (blue dots) of B and Q_{1313}^{PLY} against temperature T , with lines of best fit according to Eqn. (21). The resulting parameters of best fit are summarized in Table 1.

Fig 5. Plots of B and Q_{1313}^{PLY} against temperature T . Experimental data is shown in blue dots, whilst solid line shows line of best fit according to Eqn. (21).

Parameter	Q_{∞}^{INT} (kPa)	E_{INT} (J/mol)	Q_{∞}^{PLY} (MPa)	E_{PLY} (J/mol)	B_{∞} (Nmm ²)	E_B (J/mol)
Value	8.10×10^{-8}	5.10×10^4	1.72×10^{-9}	5.58×10^4	4.46×10^{-9}	5.75×10^4

Table 1. Summary of modelling parameters for inter-ply shear, intra-ply shear and ply bending stiffnesses.

Fundamental to this contribution is the order of magnitude different between the shear stiffness of the interface Q_{1313}^{INT} , and the shear stiffness of the ply Q_{1313}^{PLY} , in fact $Q_{1313}^{PLY} \simeq 1000 Q_{1313}^{INT}$. This large mismatch means that Cosserat effects, and therefore layer-wise bending, are fundamental to the deformation of uncured composite laminates.

4 FINTIE ELEMENT IMPLMENTATION AND MODEL VERIFICATION

In this section a brief outline of how the Cosserat equilibrium equations are solved using the finite element method. For a clamped-clamped multilayered cantilever, the formulation and implementation are verified against an experimental data from DMA tests.

The equilibrium equations (1) and (2) subject to boundary conditions can be solved using the finite element method. The domain is discretized into a uniform conforming mesh, which is either triangular ($n_e = 3$) or quadrilateral ($n_e = 4$). Nodal displacements and rotations are interpolate across elements using the piecewise linear shape functions ϕ_i so that

$$u_1 = \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \phi_i U_1^{(i)} \quad u_3 = \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \phi_i U_3^{(i)} \quad \theta_2 = \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \phi_i \theta_2^{(i)} \quad (22)$$

where $U_1^{(i)}$, $U_3^{(i)}$ and $\theta_2^{(i)}$ are the nodal displacements and rotations, and i denotes local element numbering. On an element level, nodal displacements and rotations can be related to Cosserat strain and curvature measures by the strain matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{11} \\ \gamma_{33} \\ \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{31} \\ \kappa_{21} \\ \kappa_{23} \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{B} \underline{d} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_e} \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{i,1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \phi_{i,2} & 0 \\ \phi_{i,2} & 0 & \phi_i \\ 0 & \phi_{i,1} & -\phi_i \\ 0 & 0 & \phi_{i,1} \\ 0 & 0 & \phi_{i,2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1^{(i)} \\ U_3^{(i)} \\ \theta_2^{(i)} \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

where \underline{d} is column vector of all element degrees of freedom. The element stiffness matrix is therefore given by

$$\mathbf{K}_e = \int_{\Omega_e} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C}^* \mathbf{B} dA \quad (24)$$

such that \mathbf{C}^* is the Cosserat elastic tensor and Cosserat bending tensor written in appropriate matrix form, and the rotated into global coordinates. The global stiffness matrix is the then assembled in the standard way. Furthermore, displacement boundary conditions are imposed by constructing a load vector using a Dirchlet to Neumann operator. All calculations which follow have been implemented in bespoke finite element codes in either MATLAB or freeFEM++[14].

Fig. 6. Plot of peak elastic loads against temperature for DMA experiment and Cosserat model.

Multilayered samples consisting of 16 zero degree plies are tested in the DMA machine using a similar experimental step-up as used to calculate the bending stiffness of a single ply. Each sample of length $\ell = 10\text{mm}$, is clamped at both ends, which is subjected to a sinusoidal displacement (mm) given by $u_3 = 0.3 \sin \omega t$ with $\omega = 1$ As for the single ply test, the peak elastic load is given by $f_{max} \cos \delta$, and experiments are carried out over a range of temperatures from 305K up to 375K. Figure 6 shows the peak force predicted by the Cosserat Model (solid line) against data points recorded by DMA. Good agreement is seen between experimental data and the Cosserat model, which provides confidence in the mathematical formulation, implementation and ply scale parameters derived in the preceding sections.

5 FORMATION OF OUT-OF-PLANE WRINKLING DEFECTS

The focus of this paper has been to introduce the idea of non-symmetric macroscale shear stresses in an uncured pre-preg laminate. Although a full formulation is outside the scope of this contribution, this section demonstrate the potential of the Cosserat formulation to prove low cost computational models capable of capturing the formation of wrinkling defects during manufacturing. To capture internal wrinkling instabilities within a laminate, nonlinear large deformation Cosserat rotations must be included. One author has shown that including leading order contributions of large Cosserat rotations is the minimum requirement for capturing wrinkling defects [6], including these terms equilibrium for incremental stresses and coupled-stresses have the modified equilibrium equations

$$\Delta\Sigma_{11,1} + \Delta\Sigma_{13,3} = \Sigma_{13}\Delta\theta_{2,1} + \Sigma_{33}\Delta\theta_{2,3} \quad (25)$$

$$\Delta\Sigma_{31,1} + \Delta\Sigma_{33,3} = -\Sigma_{11}\Delta\theta_{2,1} - \Sigma_{13}\Delta\theta_{2,3} \quad (26)$$

$$\Delta\Sigma_{13} - \Delta\Sigma_{31} - \Delta M_{21,1} - \Delta M_{23,3} + \Sigma_{11}\Delta\gamma_{31} - \Sigma_{33}\Delta\gamma_{13} + \Sigma_{13}\Delta\gamma_{33} - \Sigma_{31}\Delta\gamma_{11} = 0 \quad (27)$$

Here $(\cdot) = (\cdot)^{(n)} - (\cdot)^{(n-1)}$ defines the incremental operation. The derivation of these equations and the resulting nonlinear finite element formulation are given by Dodwell [6]. These equations consist of the familiar force equilibrium terms in incremental form $(\Delta\Sigma_{ij,j})$, as well as the extra terms associated with the geometric stress stiffening effects arising from a finite Cosserat rotation.

Fig. 7. (Left) Initial setup of the corner radius model (Right) the mode shape following wrinkling in the Cosserat model.

In this example the Cosserat formulation is used to predict the formation of out-of-plane wrinkles, Fig. 2 (left) as observed in a the corner radius of a 2m long C-section demonstrator [4 , Sec. 4]. This model is restricted to a single 2D corner radius of the C-section, in which 44 layers of AS4/8552 carbon fibre are consolidated by pressure q over a fixed radius of $R = 25\text{mm}$. The laminate consists of identical orthotropic layers which are rotated by either 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ or 90° about the x_2 axis, so that if Q_{ijkl}^{PLY} is the ply stiffness matrix in the 0° direction in which the stiff fibres align with the x_1 direction, rotated in the x_2 axis for all other layers. Here we consider a single periodic package consisting of fours layers with a single ply of each orientation separated by four identical orthotropic interfaces characterised by the stiffness tensor Q_{ijkl}^{INT} . Fig. 7 (left) summaries the model setup and a typical finite element mesh and boundary conditions considered. Material parameters were taken at 55°C , which is assumed constant

and uniform throughout the simulation and laminate.

The nonlinear solution scheme applies incremental loads of 1kPa. At each load step the smallest eigenvalue of the global stiffness matrix is calculated. Zero eigenvalues mark the presence of out-of-plane wrinkling bifurcation points. For this model setup and parameters the bifurcation points were identified at $q = q^* = 230\text{kPa}$. The model therefore predicts for consolidation pressures greater than q a wrinkle will form. Prior to this wrinkling instability, the laminate consolidates uniformly over the corner radius. In doing so, due the boundary conditions at the two edges, the material is preventing from shearing. This causes secondary compressive loads on the layers that is a maximum on the outside and reduces to zero at the inner boundary. Figure 7 (right) show the post buckling solutions achieved by seeding the fundamental state with the corresponding eigen-mode at q^* . The wrinkle develops with a fixed wavelength with an increasing amplitude towards the outer boundary. Figure 2 (left) shows a CT image of one of six similar wrinkles observed in the experiments, with a similar mode of deformation. Half wavelengths of the outer-most layers were measured (see. Table 2) with an average of 5.55mm. Comparing this to the Cosserat finite element results (Fig. 7 (right)) show good agreement seen, predicting a half wrinkle length of approximately 6 mm.

	1	2	3*	4	5	6	Average	Model
Wavelength (mm)	4.88	6.29	5.47	5.34	5.10	6.22	5.55	6.02

Table. 2. Half-wavelengths of size measures wrinkles observed in the demonstrator spar. Each demonstrated the same mode of wrinkling, as observed in Fig 2 (left), which corresponds to the wrinkle marked *.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A Cosserat continuum for uncured composite laminates is presented. It demonstrates the capability of capturing layer-wise mechanics on the macroscale without explicitly modelling individual layers. The model offers a robust approach, at a fraction of the computational cost when compared to classical modelling techniques. Ply scale properties (derived experimentally) for inter-ply shear, intra-ply shear and ply bending are up-scaled to macroscale Cosserat parameters for periodic arrangements of orthotropic layers have been derived. The upscaled properties show good agreement with experimental measures of bending a multi-layered stack (Sec. 4). Cosserat theory for layered structures has almost exclusively been applied to geological applications; the modelling the formation of unwanted wrinkling defects during the composite laminate manufacture represents a new application (Sec. 5). This application is particularly successful, since composite layers are thin and separated by weak interfaces, as result the modes of deformation introduced by the inclusion of Cosserat degree of freedom, in particular inter layer slip and individual ply bending, are particularly relevant and the inclusion of additional modes of deformation is not required. The model shows good agreement compared with wrinkles observed in a spar demonstrator.

There are a number of clear opportunities to extend the analysis presented here. The Cosserat model could readily be formulated for three-dimensional layered structures, although additional Cosserat parameters would have to be derived and the finite element implementation would become more complex. A future challenge is to extend these methods to non-periodic stacking sequences. Furthermore the materials are not simply elastic, often demonstrating strong plastic, rate dependent behaviour [12]. The Cosserat framework could readily be extended to include viscous constitutive behaviour. This extension further supports a modelling approach with reduced degrees of freedom, as presented here, since solutions would become time dependent requiring multiple solves.

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